

Making technology for production of bioethanol from lignocellulose economically feasible: plant wide simulations

D. Cepulyte

DTU Chemical Engineering, Technical University of Denmark
s091473@student.dtu.dk

The development of an optimal process technology for second generation bioethanol production (biological route) is still one of the major challenges facing the green production of biofuels. It is a huge technology and engineering challenge from the process design and operation point of view. This course takes on this challenge and will search for the optimization of one conventional bioethanol process flowsheet. The course will use dynamic plant model simulations to generate innovative solutions. The course will look for an optimal production of the biofuel by identifying, manipulating and fine-tuning the most critical variables presented in the complete production process.